

Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category saying the key "Safe Deposit Box" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Safe Deposit Boxes based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 19 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around Safe Deposit Boxes, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Safe Deposit Box; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

In implementing the bank's function as an intermediary in the financial system, banks have a role in providing services in the form of savings, deposits, loans and the use of services provided by the bank. This service is a support for banks' activities in competing with each other to create customer satisfaction and interest. This is what encourages banks to provide services such as safe deposit box storage services. Safe deposit box is a rental service for storing documents, goods and securities which are specially designed to be resistant to fire, water and sharp objects.

In banking financial institutions, a safe deposit box is a service in the form of renting a storage box for a customer's documents, goods and securities. Safe deposit box services are considered to provide many benefits for customers and have almost no risk. The role of banks in banking activities is of course to provide services in the form of a place to store their customers' valuables. As is the function of banks in carrying out capital providing activities, renting out safe deposit boxes, business and pensions. Based on Law No. 7 of 1992 in Article 6 letter h concerning Commercial Bank business. This article states the business activities of commercial banks, namely providing a place to store goods and securities.

According to the author, scientific publications related to safe deposit boxes are still lacking. From 2008 to 2022, there were only 20 studies regarding

safe deposit boxes. In fact, there is still no research regarding safe deposit boxes according to sharia, and most research related to safe deposit boxes is in conventional banking institutions. This shows that research regarding safe deposit boxes is still minimal, especially in Sharia Financial Institutions. Thus, it is important to carry out this research in order to find out the safe deposit box scheme at Sharia Financial Institutions.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Safe Deposit Box use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Safe Deposit Boxes, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around Safe Deposit Boxes, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Safe deposit box is a box rental service used to store documents and securities as mentioned in Law No. 10 of 1998 concerning Amendments to Law No. 7 of 1992 concerning Banking. In article 6 letter I, it is stated that banks carry out custody activities for the benefit of other parties based on a contract, as well as placing funds from customers to other customers in the form of securities that are not listed on the stock exchange. Then, in article 9 paragraph 1 it is stated that the commercial bank carrying out the deposit activities has full obligations for the goods in accordance with the contract.

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library studies (library research). The object of the research is Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Safe Deposit Boxes originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Safe Deposit Box " for the entire year (2008-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the

number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature study (library research).

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results regarding scientific publications regarding safe deposit boxes in the period 2008 to 2022 show various fluctuations every year, especially in the last 5 years. 2019 was the year with the highest number of publications about safe deposit boxes, namely 4 articles. So it can be seen that the average scientific publication regarding safe deposit boxes is around 3 articles per year.

Table 1. Article Data Regarding Safe Deposit Boxes (Based on Year)

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2008	1	2019	4
2014	1	2020	3
2016	3	2021	2
2017	1	2022	3
2018	1		
Total 19			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, we present institutions that publish publications related to safe deposit boxes in Islamic and conventional financial institutions. Diponegoro Law Journal and Student Online Journal (JOM) in the field of Legal Studies are the institutions that have published the most about safe deposit boxes, namely 3 articles.

Table 2. Institutions and Journals Publishing Scientific Publications About Safe Deposit Boxes

institution name	Number of Publications
DIPONEGORO LAW JOURNAL	3
Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Legal Studies	3
Kertha Semaya: Journal of Legal Studies	2
Advance Sustainable Science, Engineering and Technology, Engineering, Mathematics and Computer Science (EMACS) Journal, Indonesian Journal of Engineering Research, JIM Civil Law Sector, Cybernetics Journal, Journal of Electrical Engineering Jakarta Private University, Perspective, Private Law, Syiah Kuala Law Journal, Tahkim, Ultimatics: Journal of Informatics Engineering, USU LAW JOURNAL	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 presents researchers who are considered productive in publishing about safe deposit boxes, such as Budiharto and Njatrijani, Rinitami.

Table 3. Researcher Productivity Regarding Safe Deposit Boxes

Researcher	Number of Publications
Budiharto, Rinitami Njatrijani	2
Imanudin Affandi, Danny Aguswahyudi, Aminah, Puriwidi Asri, Yahya Azhari, Barus, Utary Maharany, AA Mella Silvana Chendy, Maylia Darwita, Dede Suana Ependi, Faradila Yastina, M. Raihan Febriansyah, Achmad Habibi, Metya Janastu, Devina Janice, I Gede Ketut Alit Putra Jayantara, Budi Juarto, Dheana Kartika, M. Adli, Siti Mahmudi, Naufal Majdi, Noora Qotrana Nada, Dali S. Naga, Galang Nagari, Johannes Napitupulu, Pranoto, I Made Dedy Priyanto, Hasim Purba, Ika Dya Agustina Rachmawati, Willy Sudiarto Raharjo, Rismawati, Tia Risky, Mona Rizqa, Mohamad Abdul Wahid Romadhoni, Sudimanto, Sunarmi, Ida Bagus Sutama, Wahyu Simon Tampubolon, Arsha Raulnadi Trikusuma, Hadian S. Utama, Artha Venessa, Dhimas Aria Wardhana, Yulianto, Risma Yulistiani, Rahmi Zubaedah	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Research articles regarding safe deposit boxes were carried out through searches on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garuda), resulting in 20 articles. Then the article was converted into RIS (Research Information System) format, input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Network visualization of research development maps regarding Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

of the network visualization map of research developments regarding safe deposit boxes in institutions are divided into 7 clusters and 91 topics, namely:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 26 topics, namely: arduino, blink application, bracket, branket, development, document, fingerprint, fingerprint sensor, internet, microcontroller, notification, opening, owner, password, place, robbery, safe, safe deposit box system, safe security system, security, sensor, system, theft, user, valuable, way.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 22 topics, namely: applicability, best rmsd, default glide sp, domain, flexible polypeptide, formal charge, implicit solvent mm gbsa calculation, important task, limited size, number, pose, protein, protocol, rmsd, scoring, set, small molecule, subset, success rate, time, unbound reprot structure.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 19 topics, namely: bank maybank indonesia, objects, boxes, bri, designed in a way, stored in a safe deposit box, loss of objects, crocodiles belonging to customers stored in a safe deposit box, unlawful acts, agreements, bank responsibilities, the bank, sdb, regarding consumer protection, law, law number, to maintain security, law number.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 10 topics, namely: customer, Indonesia Civil Code, Persero, Person, PT Bank Mandiri, safe deposit box leasing, safe deposit box leasing treaty, thing, treaty, valuable, thing.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 10 topics, namely: accountability, bank, bii, importance, loss, object, obligation, regulation, safe deposit box, safe deposit box agreement.
- Cluster 6. Light blue, consists of 2 topics, namely: standalone safe, system.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 2 topics, namely: conventional key, secret image.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 19 Research topics regarding Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

1. SAFE DEPOSIT BOX AUTOMATIC DOOR OPENING SYSTEM IN BANK
2. CONSUMER PROTECTION OF CUSTOMERS FOR STORAGE OF GOODS IN SAFE DEPOSIT BOX (STUDY AT PT. BANK PANIN BRANCH BANTU TEBING TINGG)
3. ASPECTS OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF SAFE DEPOSIT BOX RENTAL AGREEMENTS AT BANK MAYBANK INDONESIA
4. ANALYSIS OF SAFE DEPOSIT BOX RENTAL AGREEMENTS AT PT BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK PEKANBARU
5. Implementation of a Meaningful Sharing Scheme in Color Visual Cryptography for Digital Safe Deposit Boxes
6. CONSUMER PROTECTION AGAINST EXONERATION CLAUSES IN RENTAL AGREEMENTS - RENTING A SAFE DEPOSIT BOX AT BANK MANDIRI BANDA ACEH BRANCH
7. THE BANK'S RESPONSIBILITIES IN THE RENTAL AGREEMENT FOR RENTING A SAFE DEPOSIT BOX WHICH ALLEGEDLY CONTAINS AN EXONERATION CLAUSE (Study at PT. Bank Panin Surakarta)
8. LEGAL CONSEQUENCES OF THE INCLUSION OF AN EXONERATION CLAUSE IN SAFE DEPOSIT BOX RENTAL AGREEMENTS (CASE STUDY OF BANK INTERNATIONAL INDONESIA (BII) SAFE DEPOSIT BETTING)
9. BANK CUSTOMER PROTECTION FOR STORING VALUABLES IN A SAFE DEPOSIT BOX
10. BANK'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE OPENING OF SAFE DEPOSIT BOXES TO CUSTOMERS (CASE STUDY DECISION NUMBER 226/PDT.G/2019/PN DPS)
11. Implementation of the Safe Deposit Box Rental Agreement
12. LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST BANK CUSTOMERS WHO ARE HARMED IN SAFE DEPOSIT BOX SERVICE RENTAL AGREEMENTS
13. BII'S LIABILITY FOR LOSS OF ITEMS IN THE SAFE DEPOSIT BOX
14. JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF THE EXONERATION CLAUSE IN THE SAFE DEPOSIT BOX RENTAL AGREEMENT BETWEEN BANK BNI PEKANBARU BRANCH AND THE CUSTOMER BASED ON THE PRINCIPLE OF FREEDOM OF CONTRACT
15. Smart Safe Deposit Box Based on Internet of Things
16. Branket" Design as a Safe Deposit Box Security System using Arduino-Based Tap Sensor
17. Safe-Deposit Box Using Fingerprint and Blynk
18. SAFE DEPOSIT BOX RENTAL INFORMATION SYSTEM PT. INDEPENDENT SAFETY
19. LEGAL ASPECTS OF BANK RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE LOSS OF VALUABLE OBJECTS BELONGING TO CUSTOMERS STORED IN A SAFE DEPOSIT BOX (SDB) AND EFFORTS FOR ITS SETTLEMENT

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 19 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Safe Deposit Boxes in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

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